

Paper 25**STUDENTS SATISFACTION LEVEL IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTES-A STUDY OF PUBLIC INSTITUTES IN MANGALORE CITY.****Ms. Sulfathu Nafila MK*, Ms. Shreeraksha****

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Abstract:

Students' satisfaction has never been considered as an issue of importance by educational authorities nor regarded as a matter of survival by higher education institutions. The measurement of student satisfaction can be useful to higher education institutions, to help them to pin point their strengths and identify areas for improvement. The study measures the students' satisfaction level in higher educational public institutes in Mangalore City. Satisfaction ratings go beyond teaching assessments, which have a narrow focus, to include broader aspects of the student learning experience. To grasp the complexity of that learning experience, it is not enough to know the degree to which students are satisfied, it is important to understand the factors that contribute to student satisfaction. The purpose of this study is to identify aspects of the educational experience that are associated with students' overall expression of satisfaction and determining which features of the student experience are most closely related to satisfaction may provide information about actions that can be taken to maintain high levels of satisfaction and improve student learning.

Keywords: Higher Education, Public Institutes, Students Satisfaction.**1. INTRODUCTION**

Education sector is expanding very rapidly all over the world in recent years. Globalization and digital revolution has created a demand for new and varied disciplines in education. The cost of providing education has gone up manifold due to better teaching methodologies and learning instruments with rising inflation worldwide. Higher education is the education at a college or university level is perceived as one of most important instruments for individual social and economic development of a nation. The primary purpose of higher education is creation of knowledge and dissemination for the development of world through innovation and creativity. Students' satisfaction as a short term attitude, resulting from an evaluation of a students' educational experiences, services and facilities. It is a positive antecedent of student loyalty and is the result and outcome of an educational system. It's a students' disposition by subjective evaluation of educational outcomes and experience. Therefore, student satisfaction can be defined as a function of relative level of experiences and perceived performance about educational service during the study period.

2. OBJECTIVE & RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The objective of the study is to measure the students’ satisfaction level in higher educational public institutes in Mangalore City. This research study was done through collection of 65 respondents from Mangalore City. The research instrument used in collecting primary data was a questionnaire and survey was conducted through the means of Google form. For secondary data other sources like PDF files and internet has been used.

3. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The study was restricted only to the Mangalore city.
- The study was conducted through Google form; hence it could reach technologically literate people.
- There can be chances of bias in the response given by the respondents.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

1. Teachers Regularity.

	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied		
Satisfied		
Neutral		
Dissatisfied		7.7
Highly dissatisfied		

Table 1: depicts the students’ satisfaction regarding regularity of teachers. 38.4 percent students are highly satisfied with regularity of teachers while 40 percent students are satisfied with teacher’s regularity. 13.9 percent students are neutral and 7.7 percent students are dissatisfied with teachers’ regularity. No student is highly dissatisfied with teacher’s regularity.

2. Teacher’s Behavior in the Classroom.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	16	24.7

Satisfied	31	47.7
Neutral	10	15.3
Dissatisfied	8	12.3
Highly dissatisfied	-	-
Total	65	100

Table 2: describes the teachers' behavior towards students in the classroom. 24.7 percent students are highly satisfied and 47.7 percent students are satisfied with teachers behavior in the classroom whereas 15.3 percent students are neutral.12.3 percent students are dissatisfied with teacher behavior in the classroom and no student is highly dissatisfied with teachers' behavior in the classroom.

3. Well Equipped Labs.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	7	10.7
Satisfied	9	13.8
Neutral	27	41.5
Dissatisfied	11	17
Highly dissatisfied	11	17
Total	65	100

Table 3: shows the students satisfaction regarding labs. Only 10.7 percent students are highly satisfied and 13.8 percent students are satisfied with the labs whereas majority of the students (41.5) are neutral. 17 percent students are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied with labs in the institute.

4. IT Tools (projector, computer, digital board).

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	9	13.8
Satisfied	10	15.4
Neutral	18	27.7
Dissatisfied	18	27.7
Highly dissatisfied	10	15.4
Total	65	100

Table 04: describes the students' satisfaction regarding the availability of IT tools. A few students (13.8 percent) are highly satisfied and 15.4 percent students are satisfied with availability of IT tools in the public institutes. 27.7 percent students are neutral. Majority of the students (27.7 percent and 15.4 percent) are dissatisfied and highly dissatisfied regarding availability of IT tools in the institutes.

5. Parking Space.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	28	43.0
Satisfied	21	32.4
Neutral	10	15.4
Dissatisfied	3	4.6
Highly dissatisfied	3	4.6
Total	65	100

Table 05: highlighted the students' satisfaction regarding the parking space. Majority of the students (43 percent) are highly satisfied with the parking space 32.4 percent students are satisfied with the parking space whereas 15.4 percent students are neutral. A very few students (4.6 percent) are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied with the availability of parking space.

6. Course Fee-Structure.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	19	29.3
Satisfied	28	43.0
Neutral	14	21.7
Dissatisfied	2	3.0
Highly dissatisfied	2	3.0
Total	65	100

Table 06: shows the students satisfaction regarding the course fee structure. 29.3 percent students are highly satisfied with the course and 43.0 percent students are satisfied with the course fee while 21.7 percent students are neutral. A very few students (3.0 percent) are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied regarding course fee structure.

7. Library Facility.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	10	15.4
Satisfied	26	40.0
Neutral	10	15.4
Dissatisfied	13	20.0
Highly dissatisfied	6	9.2
Total	65	100

Table 07: describes the students' satisfaction regarding the library. 15.4 percent students are highly satisfied and 40.0 percent students are satisfied while 15.4 percent students are neutral with the library facility provided by the institutes. Only 20.0 percent students are dissatisfied and 9.2 percent students are highly dissatisfied with library facility in the institute.

8. Placement Facility.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	7	10.8
Satisfied	10	15.4
Neutral	28	43.0
Dissatisfied	10	15.4
Highly dissatisfied	10	15.4
Total	65	100

Table 08: Shows the students satisfaction regarding the placement. Only 10.8 percent students are highly satisfied and 15.4 percent students of public institutes are satisfied with the placement provided by instituted whereas 43.0 percent students are neutral. 15.4 percent students are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied with the placement facilities provided by the institutes.

9. Sports and Games Facility.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	3	4.7
Satisfied	10	15.4
Neutral	17	26.1
Dissatisfied	28	43.0
Highly dissatisfied	7	10.8
Total	65	100

Table 09: describes the student’s satisfaction regarding the sports facilities. Only 4.7 percent students are highly satisfied and 15.4 percent students are satisfied regarding sports facilities while 26.1 percent students are neutral. Majority of the students (43.0 percent)

are dissatisfied and 10.8 percent students are highly dissatisfied.

10. Extra-Curriculum Activity.

Scale	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	4	6.1
Satisfied	18	27.7
Neutral	18	27.7
Dissatisfied	17	26.2
Highly dissatisfied	8	12.3
Total	65	100

Table 10: depicts the students’ satisfaction regarding extra curriculum activities in the institutes. 6.1 percent students are highly satisfied while 27.7 percent students are satisfied regarding extra curriculum activities in the institutes. 27.7 percent students are neutral. 26.2 percent students are dissatisfied and 12.3 percent students are highly dissatisfied regarding extra curriculum activities in the public institutes.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- From our study we found that majority of the teachers are in public institutes regular.
- We got to know that majority of the students are satisfied and highly satisfied with teachers behavior in the classroom.
- From our study we found that lab facility is not up to the mark in public institutes.
- It is found that majority of the students are not satisfied regarding availability of IT tools in public institutes.
- We also realized that there is no problem of parking space in public institutes.
- It is found that majority of the students are satisfied or highly satisfied regarding fee structure in public institutes.
- Besides, we came to know that majority of the students are satisfied with library facility in the public institutes.
- On the basis of analysis it is found that majority of the respondents in public institutes are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied with placement facility.
- We could also understand that majority of the students are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied from the sports facilities provided by the public institutes.
- This study also highlights that majority of the students are dissatisfied or highly dissatisfied regarding extra curriculum activities in the public institutes.

SUGGESTIONS

- It's suggested that public institutions have to focus more and more on extra curriculum activities to develop each and every individuals.
- It's suggested that computer labs and science labs are should be expand to get more opportunity for the students to concentrate more on their practical studies.
- The public authorities need to be provided with adequate facilities and resources for effective implementation of IT tools.
- It's suggested that public institutions have to provide proper facility for sports and games thereby students can concentrate on extra curriculum activities.
- It's suggested to organize placement programs to get job opportunity to the students.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded that in public institutes students are satisfied or highly satisfied with teacher's regularity, their behavior, Parking space in the institute, Fee structure of the course and Library of public institutes. On the other hand students express their dissatisfaction regarding labs, IT tools, Placement, Sports facilities and extra curriculum activities in public institutes.

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QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Name
2. Age
3. Gender
4. How you feel about teacher's regularity in the classroom?
 - Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
5. And about teachers behavior in the classroom?
 - Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
6. How you experienced about well equipped labs?
 - Highly satisfied

- Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
7. Satisfaction on implementation of IT tools in the classroom?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
8. Satisfaction about parking space?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
9. Satisfaction on course fee-structure?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
10. Library facility provided by the public institution?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
11. Placement facility organizes by public institutes?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
12. Facilities given by public institutes for sports and games?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied

13. Satisfaction on extra-curriculum activity?
- Highly satisfied
 - Satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Dissatisfied
 - Highly dissatisfied
14. Suggestions if any.